
Using Cunningsworth's Theory to Evaluate the Libyan Second Secondary English Textbooks

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ABSTRACT: The main objective of this study is to evaluate English language textbooks in the Libyan second secondary school. In this study, the researcher used a document analysis method. The data of this research were taken from an English textbook which is 21st century English for Libya literary department of Libyan secondary 2 textbooks. Cunningsworth theory was the primary methodological tool employed by the researcher in this study. The English Textbook of The Libyan Second Secondary School's strengths is using the criteria of objectives and approaches, design and organization criteria, and the skill criterion. And the weakness of The English Textbook of The Libyan Second Secondary School is in terms of Language Content. The overall score of the fulfillment of the suitability of the textbook was 106 points for the evaluation of the Language Textbook Of The Libyan Second Secondary Textbook based on Cunningsworth's Theory. The fulfillment scores were on average 77 percent good. As a result, the Libyan Second Secondary School English Textbook was adequate. Suggestions on the Importance of English in Modern-Day Libya is that the distribution of both facilities and facilities, access to being actively involved in speaking English is one solution.

KEYWORDS: Cunningsworth's Theory, textbook evaluation, teaching material, content analysis

INTRODUCTION

In the teaching and learning of English as a Second Language (ESL), textbooks play an important role by providing teachers and students with helpful, ready-made content (Charalambous, 2011: 99). Instructors and students, on the other hand, may suffer as a result of poor course book utilization. When learning a new language, a textbook plays a critical role. Teachers and students should be aware of the importance of picking a textbook. Teachers need to think about a variety of factors when it comes to the textbook. The content should be compatible with the current curriculum as well as the educational goals of the pupils. According to Mohamed (2013: 55) The choice of textbooks has a significant impact on whether or not pupils succeed in school. This indicates that the textbook utilized in the learning-teaching process has a direct impact on the students' growth and achievement in the course of their studies.

The process of creating new textbooks necessitates a thorough assessment of current ones. Problems with existing textbooks can be used to determine the direction of the future creation of new teaching aids (Lee, 2013: 75). The cover of every textbook is different. The cover, title, or content may be to blame for the change in appearance. A textbook's level of quality also displays its differences. The author can employ a variety of approaches to convey the information in the book. Mohamed, (2013: 69) can't guarantee that the textbook fits the standards for a good textbook, even if they stress the importance of the curriculum in their study. To establish if a textbook meets the criteria for a good textbook, an evaluation must be conducted. A textbook's quality can be greatly improved by a thorough examination.

Finding out how much students and teachers respect a given textbook is an important part of the evaluation process. It is critical to consider the views and experiences of language teachers when developing textbooks and other instructional materials (Abdullah & Hammad, 2014: 16). It is also important to consider the context (teachers' and students' needs and interests) in which the textbook materials will be used while selecting them. As a result, teachers must be included in the review process at all costs. The comments of the textbook's users, teachers and students, must be gathered to improve or develop the textbook's usability (Kim, 2015: 10). Examining English as a Foreign Language (EFL) teachers' perceptions of instructional materials might provide useful information regarding those resources (Hammad & Abdellatif, 2012: 133). It is also stated by Shabani and Safari, (2017: 115) that EFL teachers have a right to participate in the review of English textbooks because they are the actual users.

Three methods of materials evaluation are proposed by Cunningsworth, (1995): pre-use, in-use and post-use. When teachers have

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no previous experience with the book, pre-use evaluation is used. A textbook evaluation that takes place while the materials are being used is known as an "in-use" evaluation. When a textbook is used for a long length of time, it is possible to discern strengths and shortcomings that become apparent with time. Cunningsworth's theory has several advantages. According to Tomlinson (2011), post-use assessment is the examination of what happened after utilizing the materials. Material strengths and shortcomings are identified in this sort of review, allowing users to reflect on their usage of the materials and let them decide if they will use them again in the future. Evaluators may be able to determine the strengths and limitations of materials during in-use evaluation; however, they may not be able to detect the issues that may arise over time (Cunningsworth, 1995). As a result, the findings of this study will be put to good use in a post-use evaluation of the textbook.

Students take a state-administered exam after ninth grade to decide whether they are eligible to attend secondary schools and institutes. Students who succeed are given a certificate that allows them to enroll in secondary school (upper secondary school). Students who perform poorly on this exam will not be permitted to attend public school. They have the option of going to a vocational school or joining the military. The C-Phase (2). For three years, intermediate education (secondary school) includes specialized secondary schools and technical and vocational centers and institutes, as well as colleges. You cannot enroll in any major in secondary school unless you meet the minimum score requirements for that particular major. There is a limit to the number of specializations you can pursue if you have a lower than 85% score in Biology and Physics. Students must pass a state examination after their three-year study period to be admitted to universities and other post-secondary institutions. Secretary of Education and Scientific Research administers this state examination. The results of the exams are made public in major publications and on the internet.

There are seven years of preparatory and secondary-school-level English required for Libyan second-secondary students. An emphasis is placed on consolidating and expanding knowledge of the grammatical system, enhancing the student's proficiency in the four language skills of reading, listening, speaking, and writing; this course is meant to do so. There are vocabulary and topic categories that complement the students' selected academic areas and reinforce learning in each lesson through the use of specialist material.

To evaluate the English textbook, we will apply Cunningsworth's theory, which has the standards necessary for a quality textbook and also provides students with both language input and output to aid their language learning

METHODOLOGY

The purpose of this study was to determine the value of English textbooks in two ways. The first step was to see if the textbook analyzed satisfied the criteria synthesized from those proposed by the authors (Hayton et al., 2015: 194). Second, it made an effort to figure out how those requirements were met. To get a clearer picture of this issue, all parts of English textbooks were examined. To supplement the descriptive analysis, researchers will conduct interviews with teachers after receiving their findings. Consolidation of vocabulary and grammar, as well as practice in the four skills, is a major focus of the textbooks' activities. As a result, students can tailor their language learning experience to their interests and abilities. All of the listening passages, activities, and phonics from the textbook and workbook are included in the audio extracts. Because it was classified as content analysis research, the researcher served as the principal instrument in this investigation. The researcher was a crucial instrument in this investigation because it made use of a human instrument (Cunningsworth, 1995). The researcher's responsibilities also include collecting data, analyzing the data, and reporting the findings. Cunningsworth theory was the primary methodological tool employed by the researcher in this study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Strength and Weaknesses of the English Textbook of the Libyan Second Secondary School

Strengths

Supporting materials like CDs and transcripts are included in the English textbook for the second secondary school in Libya to help with listening comprehension exercises. Additionally, although the publisher exclusively produces books for students, this book does have instructor editions. Although each topic is distinct yet connected to the others, the information in English book 2 is grouped by topic. According to the study's findings, each chapter's content is presented in a skill- and level-based order. The physical look of the textbook is likewise pleasing and vibrant. This book is intriguing because of its vibrant illustrations.

Speaking, reading, writing, and listening are the four skills covered in this book. The exercises in this book often start with listening skills, then go on to speaking, reading, and writing. Each chapter of this book has one or more of these exercises. For instance, during a listening exercise, students are required to hear and comprehend a discussion about a societal topic or problem. There are several integrated skill tasks in the English textbook for the second secondary school in Libya. Each resource or assignment in this book has interconnected activities. Each action often combines two or more abilities, such as speaking and

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listening.

Because the content covered in this book is so closely tied to students' daily lives and may aid in the development of their knowledge, it is highly familiar, engaging, and simple for students to comprehend. The design of this book encourages and pushes students to become familiar with the scientific method, which entails observing, asking questions, accumulating facts, associating, and communicating, by immersing them in an environment of inquiry learning.

The material in the English textbook for the Libyan Second Secondary School has been tailored to the needs of the students and is based on their daily life, so the themes covered in the textbook can be utilized in casual conversation. This book's content can assist pupils to gain better oral and written communication abilities. This textbook's companion teacher's book, which may be able to offer extra resources for instructors in the learning process, is another strength. Additionally, this book includes audio in the form of a tape to expose pupils to English because the proper pronunciation of English is required from an early age. It incorporates four language skills, one of which is listening abilities.

Weaknesses

Language Content has a weakness since a few of the sub-criteria have not been satisfied. The English textbook for The Libyan Second Secondary School includes a unique session at the end named "Grammar and Function Reference" that covers the grammar part in detail. Because grammar is covered towards the conclusion of the book with brief explanations, it will be challenging for students to grasp. The grammar information offered in this book is incomplete and does not meet the standards for a good textbook. So my solution to overcoming this weakness is to add some sub-criteria in English textbooks for Libyan secondary schools including grammar and some of its functions so that they are rearranged more attractively, systematically and filled with clearer descriptive information so that students will find it easier to understand it and according to the standards of a good textbook.

Aims and Approaches

The English Textbook of the Libyan Second Secondary School is categorized as "appropriate" with the criteria of aims and approaches. It is because the material presented has been adapted to the needs and is based on the daily lives of students, as the topics taught in textbooks are topics that can be used for everyday conversation. The material in this book can help improve students' skills both in oral and written form. Based on the results obtained, this book is very good for students as a learning resource because all the material has been adapted to the curriculum and is close to the daily lives of students so it can make it easier to achieve learning goals. Each material presented contains a description of text elements such as social functions, text structure, and linguistic elements. There are also integrated activities of the four skills, namely listening, speaking, reading and writing so this book is included in the comprehensive book category. For example, the learning objectives apply social functions, text structures, and linguistic elements of spoken and written transactional interaction texts that involve the act of giving and asking for information related to suggestions and offers; compose transactional interaction texts, spoken and written, short and simple, which involve the act of giving and asking for information related to suggestions and offers.

Design and Organization

Based on the design and organization criteria, the English Textbook Of The Libyan Second Secondary School is categorized as "Appropriate" because the English Textbook Of The Libyan Second Secondary School has supporting components such as CDs and transcripts to support listening skills activities. Also, this book does provide teacher books, the publisher only publishes books for students. The material presented in English book 2 is organized by topic, although each topic is different but is related to one another. From the results of the study, it was found that the material contained in each chapter has an order based on skill and level.

Layout and Physical Appearance of the Textbook

Based on Cunningsworth's theory, the layout and physical appearance of the English Textbook of the Libyan Second Secondary School has good paper quality so that the textbook is durable (quality of paper and binding). Besides, the size of the textbook seems convenient for students to handle because it is not too thick and is the right size for students. The cover of the textbook is appealing and the main headings and subheadings are well-organized. The units are well organized and offer easy progression can be seen from the table contents.

The textbook contains enough pictures, diagrams, tables, etc. To help the students understand the printed texts. Illustrations, tables, figures, graphs, etc. Are relevant and functional. The textbook is provided the necessary audio-visual aids, which help students learn the four skills in an integrated way. However, an adequate vocabulary list or glossary is included but not very clear and the instructions in the textbook are written in a simple and clear language also, the material contains adequate indices and appendices.

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The Content of the Textbook

English Textbook Of The Libyan Second Secondary School contains an appropriate table of content and the content does not conflict with students' backgrounds. The textbook covers most language skills with the subject matter presented either topically or functionally in a logical, organized manner and also sufficient variety in the subject and content of the textbook. The content contains real-life issues that challenge the reader to think critically about his/her worldview. The content promotes students' involvement so the textbook is appropriate for the learners' level. The material encourages a positive attitude towards gender. (e.g. stereotyping occupation or use of gender bias words like chairman instead of chairperson). The textbook encourages a positive attitude towards environmental issues. The contents of the textbook are the following characteristics that must be met to have an excellent textbook, according to Yolanda (2018: 190), namely, a well-written textbook helps motivate students to learn. Students can readily learn on their own if the textbooks can grab their interest. Good textbooks are connected to other books. Readers can apply what they learn here to any other textbook that has a similar focus in terms of subject matter.

The Objectives of the Textbook

The objectives in the textbook are clear and precise for the learners, gradual in difficulty and realistic. The objectives of the materials correspond to the needs of the learners and also recognize individual differences so the materials suit the level of the learners and can be covered within the time allocated for the textbook. Textbooks have a clear purpose to help improve student skills and make it easier for teachers to teach. Teachers can draw inspiration from textbooks while planning classroom activities (Athawadi, 2019: 8). In addition, textbooks can be used as part of the curriculum in some cases. Teachers must choose the ideal textbook for their classroom's needs and the curriculum as a whole while planning activities for their students. The textbook must meet the criteria of a strong textbook in terms of materials, including exercises and the ability to demonstrate proficiency in a certain skill. Based on the picture below, shows that the objective of this textbook is that after studying the things in the textbook, students will be able to get or improve the skills being taught. The lessons in this book, as shown in Figure 4.17 also show that the lessons are related to everyday life so that students can relate to the lessons and are easier and can be applied in everyday life.

The Language Type of the Textbook

The language used in the textbook is authentic i.e. like real-life English and includes materials for pronunciation work, e.g. individual sound, word stress, intonation, etc. There is an emphasis on language use and learners are given examples of ways they can use their foreign language in the future beyond the school experience. But there are no new and critical concepts defined in the glossary or explained when they are first introduced in the text. Based on the picture, it can be seen how the type of language used is good. It is also shown that the textbook has keywords that students can use to know how to pronounce words correctly but there is no glossary.

The Language Skills of the Textbook

The material provides the four language skills. Listening is accompanied by activities that help comprehension. Spoken English (dialogues, role play, communication activities, etc. Are designed to equip learners for real-life interaction. The reading passages are associated with pre/while/post-reading activities. Relevant skills are catered for in the textbook such as critical thinking, problem-solving, etc. But the textbook is lacking in paying attention to writing activities such as controlled, guided, and free paragraphs.

Activities and Tasks in the Textbook

In the textbook, the grammatical rules are presented logically and in increasing order of difficulty so the new structure is integrated into varying contexts and situations. The grammatical points are presented with brief and easy examples and explanations and the vocabulary load seems to be reasonable for the level of the learners. There is sufficient written practice of the grammatical concepts that lead to communicative use of the language. The progression of vocabulary items is appropriate, functional, thematic, authentic, and practical. There is also sufficient oral practice of the grammatical concepts that leads to communicative use of the language. But the new vocabulary words are not presented in a variety of ways and are not presented at an appropriate rate so that the text is understandable. So this provides input and suggestions for criticism for the next curriculum to be improved so that in the future it is presented in tabular form so that it is easy for readers to understand.

Suggestions About the Importance of English in Modern-Day Libya

The ability to speak English is important for one's competitiveness. With good English skills, good competitiveness, which is useful for our country as well. " But that doesn't mean we have to forget the Libyan language, which has become the national language. Language is one element of education as a learning material in both formal and non-formal educational institutions,

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about the portrait of English language education in Indonesia, we do not only think about schools in urban areas. Based on research conducted by the world education institution, EF English First announced the first comprehensive report, on the EF English Proficiency Index (EF EPI) in 44 countries. English proficiency in Indonesia is very low at 34th, while Malaysia is through. in 9th place. The EF EPI is the first index to compare the English proficiency of adults in different countries. This index uses unique test data (specific methodology) on more than two million people in 44 countries, who used free online tests over three years (2007-2009) (Fisher, 2011).

As a first step towards the current portrait of English language education in Libya, from the point of view of equal distribution of education, it cannot be ignored. Schools located in big cities or schools that have many luxurious facilities to support learning or schools that are specially designed like an international standard school. In general, there seems to be a dividing line in the distribution of English language education between the city and the suburbs, between most government schools and private schools. students in the city are far more fortunate than those in the suburbs. For example, students in cities can easily take English courses either with local teachers or native speakers, easy access to study materials, and various other conveniences of English language programs. On the other hand, students in suburban areas often study in limited circumstances.

Based on the description above, the distribution of both facilities and facilities that function as supporters in the learning process also has a different impact, students or students who study English in urban areas have better English skills than suburban students. One answer is access to being actively involved in speaking English. So it can be concluded that one of the keys to being able to master English well is to actively continue to use English or be actively involved in the use of English (target language) as most do. students in urban areas.

The first attention is focused on the curriculum that has been set at the school and whether it has been able to contribute to improving English language education or not. In general, the curriculum made by the school has not been able to make students in Libya able to actively speak English. Furthermore, judging from the intensity of learning English in Libya, nowadays children already have a lot of time to learn English. Logically and theoretically, the implications are easy to understand, if children have a lot of time to learn English, they will quickly be able to speak English, especially since they learn English from an early age.

Observing the position of English as a foreign language is the main reason why our children's abilities are low. In theory, we can understand that if we view English as a foreign language, it will certainly be different if we see English as a second language or L2 (second communication tool) as in Malaysia and Singapore where English is used in people's lives in addition to the main/official language. In Libya, English is only learned in school but is not used in everyday life. That is why English in Libya is generally taught as a foreign language. The term 'foreign language' in the field of language teaching is different from 'second language'. A foreign language is a language that is not used as a means of communication in a particular country where the language is taught. While a second language is a language that is not the main language but becomes one of the common languages in a country. If we return it based on the notion of language as a system of communication in speech and writing used by people of a particular country. Thus, the status of the language as a mother tongue, second language, or foreign language will also have an impact on the purpose of a language to be learned.

English as a foreign language has the meaning that English is only used and is located as a learning institution in an educational institution, both formal educational institutions and non-formal educational institutions and is not used as a language in social life and daily life interactions nor is it a language. basis in a country (Tomlinson, 2005). This shows that English is only studied in terms of theory and science. This is certainly contrary to the concept of learning a language: where learning a language is learning 4 language skills: listening, speaking, reading and writing. In the learning process that is located as a foreign language, each student must acquire an approach by emphasizing the habituation and ability (speaking, reading, writing and listening) to use the language they have learned.

Some of the characteristics of foreign language learning carried out in schools are:

- a. The purpose of a foreign language learning method is to practice, educate, and be cultured. In foreign language learning, the practice of the language being studied is the most important thing that must be done by students. That is, the teacher not only provides knowledge about pronunciation, structure, or sentence structure but also creates a language interaction, especially from foreign languages that have been obtained by students. Students, it aims to get a mental boost as well as sharpen the development of knowledge.
- b. The method used uses several principles:
 - 1) Spoken language is the basic principle used by teachers in the learning process.
 - 2) Students are given an understanding of the material to be taught orally before reading or writing.
 - 3) Prioritizing active learning
 - 4) Emphasizing the practice carried out by students

In communicating, knowledge of the linguistic order is needed, the linguistic order helps students to choose the form of

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speech in communication, and the meaning and function of the speech itself. Linguistic order alone is not enough (Tomlinson, 2005).

The primary idea of learning English as a foreign language is the application of English itself in a social context, that is, language is utilized in social interactions (Tomlinson, 2005). While it may seem counterintuitive, real-world English use can be a crucial part of learning a new language. In other words, just because a student has a huge vocabulary doesn't mean they'll be able to communicate effectively in English. Likewise, just because a student can recall all of the different grammar structures and tenses doesn't mean they'll be able to write clearly in English.

CONCLUSION

The English Textbook of The Libyan Second Secondary School is classed as "Appropriate" using the criteria of objectives and approaches, according to the findings of the analysis. The English Textbook of The Libyan Second Secondary School is classed as "Appropriate" based on the design and organization criteria since various design and organization sub-criteria have not been satisfied. Because multiple sub-criteria have not been satisfied, this book can be classified as "Not Appropriate" in terms of Language Content. The English Textbook Of The Libyan Second Secondary School classifies the skill criterion as "Appropriate". Speaking, reading, writing, and listening are the four skills covered in his book. The English Textbook Of The Libyan Second Secondary School covers a wide range of topics. Each unit has a distinct topic. Every topic in the book has been tailored to fit the requirements of the relevant curriculum. The scientific approach is one of the strategies utilized in the curriculum for teaching and learning. The English Textbook Of The Libyan Second Secondary School is by use of the scientific approach technique, according to the study findings. A teacher's book is included in the Libyan Second Secondary School English Textbook. This is one of the book's strengths since if there is a teacher's book, it is very easy for teachers to implement this book in class properly and appropriately.

It is quite simple for instructors to correctly and adequately utilize this book in the classroom. The overall score of the fulfillment of the suitability of the textbook was 106 points for the evaluation of the Language Textbook Of The Libyan Second Secondary Textbook based on Cunningsworth's Theory. The fulfillment scores were on average 77 percent good. As a result, the Libyan Second Secondary School English Textbook was adequate.

Suggestions on the Importance of English in Modern-Day Libya is that the distribution of both facilities and facilities that serve as supporters in the learning process has a different impact, with students or students who study English in urban areas having better English skills than students who study English in suburban areas. Access to being actively involved in speaking English is one solution. As a result, one of the keys to mastering English is to actively continue to use English or to be actively involved in the use of English (target language), as most students in metropolitan areas do.

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